

Conference Abstract

Dynamics of carbon and nitrogen in soils and european beech (*Fagus Sylvatica L.*) saplings after the stand's canopy opening

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Received: 30 Apr 2025 | Published: 02 Jun 2025

Citation: Damyanova S, Anev S (2025) Dynamics of carbon and nitrogen in soils and european beech (*Fagus Sylvatica L.*) saplings after the stand's canopy opening. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e157529. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e157529>

Abstract

The carbon and nitrogen dynamics in soils and different parts of European beech saplings were investigated following the opening of the stand's canopy by forest cuttings or natural disturbances. The study was conducted in four sample plots at the LTER forest site 'Petrohan' in Western Bulgaria. Compared to closed-canopy control plots, an increase in the carbon content of beech saplings was observed in areas with open canopies due to forest cuttings, suggesting acclimation. Conversely, following a large-scale forest disturbance caused by windthrow, the carbon content in beech saplings decreased compared to that under an undisturbed canopy. The carbon content of saplings in all plots decreased in the following order: leaves, roots, stems, and branches. Meanwhile, nitrogen content was highest in the leaves, followed by stems and branches, and was lowest in the roots.

Keywords

carbon, nitrogen, soils, European beech saplings, canopy opening

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Presented at

POSTER

Acknowledgements

The research that led to these results was carried out with the help of infrastructure LTER-BG (Agreement № TO1-320/30.11.2023), purchased under the National Roadmap for Scientific Infrastructure, financially coordinated by the Ministry of Education and Science, Bulgaria.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.